

Transportation Research Part D

Relationship between temperature and road traffic noise under actual continuous vehicle flow --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	TRD-D-21-00789R2
Article Type:	VSI: Transportation Noise
Keywords:	Road traffic noise; temperature correction; noise generation; in situ measurements; normalisation; noise mapping
Corresponding Author:	David Montes González SPAIN
First Author:	Manuel Sánchez-Fernández
Order of Authors:	Manuel Sánchez-Fernández Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas, Dr. David Montes González, Dr. Guillermo Rey Gozalo, Dr.
Abstract:	<p>This paper focuses on studying the influence of temperature on the sound pressure level of tire-road noise emission using continuous environmental noise measurements. In situ noise measurements were performed next to a primary road under free flowing traffic where tire-road noise emission dominates, while simultaneously monitoring the air and pavement temperature. The broadband results showed a variation in noise level with temperature, with a ratio of -0.058 ± 0.007 dBA/°C for the pavement temperature and -0.161 ± 0.020 dBA/°C for the air temperature. A 1/3 octave band analysis revealed a decrease in sound level with increasing temperature in the fundamental bands of road traffic noise emission, and similar behaviour and values to that observed in the broadband analysis. The physical media in which temperature is measured appears to be important. Several implications may arise from this work in regard to reference standards for noise evaluation, calculation and measurement</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Pavlos Kassomenos University of Ioannina, Greece pkassom@uoi.gr Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and cited in the manuscript</p> <p>Paulo Henrique Trombetta Zannin Federal University of Curitiba zannin@ufpr.br Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and cited in the manuscript</p> <p>Virginia Puyana-Romero Universidad de Las Américas, Quito, Ecuador virginia.puyana@udla.edu.ec Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and cited in the manuscript</p> <p>Carlos Iglesias-Merchan Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain carlos.iglesias@upm.es Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and cited in the manuscript</p>
Response to Reviewers:	

Highlights

- A decrease of noise with increasing temperature was found under real conditions
- Variations of the coefficients for air and pavement temperatures were observed
- A normalisation of traffic flow improved the explanation of noise variability
- A previously unknown increase in noise level with temperature at 160 Hz was noted

1 Relationship between temperature and road traffic noise under actual 2 conditions of continuous vehicle flow

3 Manuel Sánchez-Fernández^{a,b}, Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas^a, David Montes
4 González^{a*}, Guillermo Rey Gozalo^a

5 ^a INTERRA, Lambda, Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidad de Extremadura,
6 Avda. de la Universidad s/n, 10003 Cáceres, Spain.

7 ^b INTERRA, NEXUS, Universidad de Extremadura, Avda. de la Universidad s/n, 10003
8 Cáceres, Spain.

9 *Corresponding author. E-mail address: davidgm@unex.es

10 ABSTRACT

11 This paper focuses on studying the influence of temperature on the sound pressure
12 level of tire-road noise emission using continuous environmental noise measurements.
13 *In situ* noise measurements were performed next to a primary road under free flowing
14 traffic where tire- road noise emission dominates, while simultaneously monitoring the
15 air and pavement temperature. The broadband results showed a variation in noise level
16 with temperature, with a ratio of -0.058 ± 0.007 dBA/°C for the pavement temperature
17 and -0.161 ± 0.020 dBA/°C for the air temperature. A 1/3 octave band analysis revealed
18 a decrease in sound level with increasing temperature in the fundamental bands of road
19 traffic noise emission, and similar behaviour and values to that observed in the
20 broadband analysis. The physical media in which temperature is measured appears to be
21 important. Several implications may arise from this work in regard to reference
22 standards for noise evaluation, calculation and measurement.

23 **Keywords:** road traffic noise; temperature correction; noise generation; *in situ*
24 measurements; normalisation; noise mapping.

25 **1. INTRODUCTION**

26 This paper presents an experimental study of the relationships between
27 temperature and environmental noise level generated by road traffic on a primary road.
28 The tire-road noise emission is analysed for a mixed traffic under road operating
29 conditions and for a dense asphalt. *In situ* noise measurements were performed in both
30 broadband and frequency bands, while simultaneously monitoring the temperature of
31 both the air and the pavement. This approach allows an approximation to this question
32 by considering a mixed traffic flow including both light and heavy vehicles
33 simultaneously, unlike research under controlled conditions.

34 The noise generated by road traffic is a source of environmental pollution that has
35 adverse effects on the general population (Cai et al., 2020; Lan et al., 2020; Ma et al.,
36 2021; Thacher et al., 2020) and on wildlife (Connelly et al., 2020; Finch et al., 2020;
37 Iglesias-Merchán et al., 2016). Road traffic noise is also closely related to air pollution
38 and its impacts on people's health (Andersson et al., 2020; Franklin and Fruin, 2017;
39 Puyana-Romero et al., 2020). In this context, the European Environmental Noise
40 Directive (European Directive, 2002) considers this type of infrastructure the main
41 source of noise pollution, and requires the use of strategic noise maps (Barrigón
42 Morillas et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2021; Lan and Cai, 2021; Wosniacki and Zannin,
43 2021) to provide a basis for assessing the environmental impact and for the design of
44 measures for noise mitigation (Fredianelli et al., 2019; Montes-González et al., 2019;
45 Paschalidou et al., 2019).

46 Factors influencing the noise levels from roads can be classified into three groups:
47 infrastructure characteristics, traffic characteristics and environmental conditions.
48 Infrastructure characteristics are variables that can be controlled during the process of
49 designing, modifying or maintaining roads, and these include the type of pavement, the
50 state of conservation, and the geometric design. Vázquez et al. (V. F. Vázquez et al.,
51 2018) found that the dynamic stiffness and the macrotexture of cold in-place recycled
52 pavement are more important conditioning factors in the generation of tyre/road noise at
53 medium frequencies than for other conventional hot bituminous mixtures. They also
54 evaluated the medium-term evolution of the surface features of urban pavements, such
55 as the rolling noise and mean profile depth (MPD), and concluded that the MPD may be
56 related to pavement ageing and hence to the evolution of the tyre/pavement noise
57 (Víctor F. Vázquez et al., 2018). Del Pizzo et al. (Del Pizzo et al., 2020) identified a
58 positively correlated zone for low frequency emission and a negatively correlated region
59 at higher frequencies, by analysing 10 road surfaces in terms of their CPX noise and
60 texture levels. Licitra et al. carried out a study that demonstrated the importance of the
61 type of tyre on the sound pressure level generated on low-noise road surfaces (Licitra et
62 al., 2017).

63 Compared to factors associated with the infrastructure itself, the characteristics of
64 the traffic (such as the flow, speed, vehicle typology, intrinsic characteristics or tyres)
65 are more difficult to control. Rey Gozalo et al. (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019) observed a
66 clear influence from the number and percentage of heavy vehicles on the uncertainty in
67 noise maps, and found it hard to estimate the traffic speed in connection with noise
68 mapping. The speed and vehicle typology are widely studied parameters that also
69 condition the sound pressure level generated in tyre-road noise (Cho and Mun, 2008;
70 Institute for Vehicle Technology, 2005).

71 Meteorological factors also affect both the propagation and the generation of
72 sound energy. Standards for the assessment of environmental noise generally consider
73 propagation in a broad way, but often do not clearly address issues related to noise
74 generation (ISO 1996-1, 2016; ISO 1996-2, 2017; ISO 9613-1, 1993; ISO 9613-2,
75 1996). In this regard, ISO 11819-1, ISO 11819-2 and ISO/PAS 11819-4 (ISO/PAS
76 11819-4, 2013; ISO 11819-1, 1997; ISO 11819-2, 2017) cover the assessment of
77 tyre/road noise and do not cover environmental noise emissions from road traffic. ISO
78 11819-1 standard (ISO 11819-1, 1997) indicates that sound levels should be corrected
79 to a reference air temperature of 20°C, but does not go so far as to propose a specific
80 way to make this correction. ISO 11819-2 (ISO 11819-2, 2017) also establishes a
81 reference air temperature of 20°C and proposes a temperature correction of the sound
82 level based on a coefficient given in ISO/TS 13471-1:2017 (ISO/TS 13471-1, 2017) that
83 is only valid for two specific tires and not for a general circulation fleet. The value of
84 this coefficient varies between -0.04 and -0.11 dBA/°C according to the type of surface
85 and the speed of the vehicles. Values of between -0.05 and -0.10 were also proposed as
86 standard for three different types of road surfaces, but these were independent of speed.
87 The influence of air and pavement temperature on the generation of sound pressure
88 levels has been explored by several researchers (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007;
89 Bueno et al., 2011; Bühlmann et al., 2015; Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011; Jabben, 2013;
90 Kneib et al., 2016; Liao et al., 2015; Sandberg, 2015; Yuan et al., 2019) who based their
91 studies on reference standards for the acoustic characterisation of pavements under
92 controlled traffic conditions (ISO/PAS 11819-4, 2013; ISO 11819-2, 2017). Bühlmann
93 and Van Blokland carried out a review where a great variety of results were shown for
94 the relationship between tyre-road noise and temperature. (Bühlmann and Van
95 Blokland, 2014). To the best of the present authors' knowledge, there have been no

96 studies in which the effect of temperature on the sound level of a road transport
97 infrastructure has been measured under actual conditions of continuous vehicle flow.
98 Jabben (Jabben, 2013) conducted a study in which the maximum sound pressure level,
99 (LAmax), recorded for individual vehicles in a free flowing traffic was analysed. Prior
100 analyses carried out under these standards have examined the effect of temperature on
101 the sound pressure level generated as a function of variables such as pavement porosity
102 and the types of tyres, vehicles and pavement. In these studies, the relationship between
103 sound pressure level and air or pavement temperature has generally been determined by
104 means of linear relationships, and the values found for the coefficients ranged between
105 -0.03 and -0.11 dBA/°C. In some of these works, an analysis of this effect in the 1/3
106 octave bands has also been carried out, and the results have shown different behaviours
107 depending on the frequency (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007; Bueno et al., 2011;
108 Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011). As a general rule, a higher linear relationship between
109 temperature and sound level has been observed in frequency ranges of 31.5–630 Hz and
110 1.6–5 kHz, where the coefficients are mostly negative. However, the ISO/TS 13471-
111 1:2017 standard (ISO/TS 13471-1, 2017) points out that the data collected in this way
112 are not sufficiently consistent to allow for a frequency-dependent temperature
113 correction, and therefore suggests that the same correction should be applied for all
114 frequencies. In this regard, the recently proposed Common Noise Assessment Methods
115 in Europe (CNOSSOS-EU) (European Directive, 2015) for strategic noise mapping uses
116 a correction to the sound power emitted by road traffic to reflect the decrease with
117 increasing air temperature. Based on a broadband analysis, CNOSSOS-EU proposes the
118 application of a generic coefficient of -0.08 dB/°C for light vehicles (category 1) and
119 -0.04 dB/°C for heavy vehicles (categories 2 and 3) for all asphalts, while for octave

120 band analyses, these same correction coefficients are applied to all octave bands from
121 63 Hz to 8 kHz, without distinguishing between low, medium and high frequencies.

122 **2. METHODOLOGY**

123 **2.1. Study area**

124 On-site measurements were carried out on the N-521 road in Extremadura, Spain,
125 in the section between the towns of Cáceres and Malpartida de Cáceres (Fig. 1). As
126 discussed below, the point of measurement was chosen based on the characteristics of
127 the road geometry, good pavement conditions, the proximity of an official speed camera
128 and the average daily traffic (ADT). It was located 5 km from Malpartida de Cáceres,
129 on a straight section of 3.4 km (plan view) with a horizontal cross section in the
130 measurement area. There were no obstacles between the microphone and the road that
131 could cause acoustic shielding effects (Montes González et al., 2020b; Van Blokland et
132 al., 2014) and no reflective surfaces behind it that could produce sound reflections
133 (Memoli et al., 2008; Montes González et al., 2020a) (Fig. 1).

134

135 Fig. 1. Location, plan view and cross-sectional profile of the measurement site.

136 The traffic flow in this section is monitored by the Ministry of Transport (Spanish
 137 National Government) using a traffic counter. Based on the data recorded over the last
 138 ten years, the ADT on this stretch of road is 7,658 vehicles, of which 7,256 are light
 139 vehicles (95.1%) and 378 are heavy vehicles (4.9%). It can therefore be estimated that it
 140 has an annual flow that is close to the limit of three million vehicle passages established
 141 by the European Environmental Noise Directive (European Directive, 2002) at which it
 142 would be considered a major road. An estimated value of 600 vehicles per hour during
 143 the day could be expected based on the ADT.

144 This is a seven-year-old road surface that can be assumed to be a dense asphalt. Its
145 wearing course is composed of 8 cm of bituminous concrete AC22S in the lower layer,
146 and 3 cm of discontinuous bituminous mix BBTM 11B in the upper part (Ministry of
147 Transport of Spain, 2015). The discontinuous bituminous mix BBTM 11B has a void
148 content greater than 12% and a surface macrotexture greater than 1.5 mm (see Fig. 2).
149 The parameters of percentage of voids and MPD were measured when the pavement
150 was laid. These data were provided by the Ministry of Transport, Mobility and Urban
151 Agenda. This surface corresponds to the NL01 class, in accordance with CNOSSOS-EU
152 (European Directive, 2015). The area adjacent to the road was mainly grass, and could
153 be considered acoustically absorbent (Fig. 1).

154
155 Fig. 2. Details of the road surface

156 2.2. Measurement procedure

157 In order to analyse the effect of temperature on the noise generated under actual
158 conditions of continuous vehicle flow, the study needed to be designed in such a way
159 that the variables or conditions that could influence the measured sound level were
160 taken into account throughout the experimental procedure.

161 The obvious first step was to consider the variability in the characteristics of the
162 passing vehicles, their typology and the numbers of vehicles driving past the
163 microphone within a given unit of time.

164 There is a wide range of types of vehicle, and the maintenance conditions for both
165 the vehicles and the tyres also vary. In order to obtain a suitable average of their effects
166 on the noise level, the measurement time was selected to ensure that at least 100
167 vehicles passed in front of the measurement point. Based on the official ADT, a
168 measurement time of 10 minutes was selected.

169 The speed limit on the stretch of road under study was 100 km/h, and an official
170 speed camera was located close to the measuring point (Fig. 1). Measurements at this
171 point showed that the average speed of the vehicles was slightly lower than the speed
172 limit, and that the majority of the vehicles were travelling at within ± 5 km/h of the
173 average speed. Maximum variations of about 1 dBA were estimated for light and heavy
174 vehicles for variations in speed of ± 5 km/h (Institute for Vehicle Technology, 2005).
175 The variability in sound level associated with vehicle speed was averaged over a total
176 number of passing vehicles that was equal to or greater than 100, in the same way as for
177 the vehicle characteristics (ISO 11819-1, 1997).

178 The noise level generated by traffic will also depend on the category of the
179 vehicle. The category and flow of vehicles were visually monitored for each lane of
180 traffic, and four categories of vehicle were identified based on CNOSSOS-EU
181 (European Directive, 2015), as follows: Category 1: light motor vehicles; Category 2:
182 medium heavy vehicles; Category 3: heavy vehicles; Category 4: powered two-
183 wheelers. The last of these had two subcategories: Category 4A: mopeds; Category 4A:
184 motorcycles.

185 As indicated above, only about 5% of the traffic did not fall into the category of
186 light vehicles, meaning that its effect on the variability in the different measurements of
187 the equivalent continuous sound level may not be significant. However, its possible
188 effect was evaluated in this study by using an equivalence factor between the different
189 vehicle typologies and light vehicles, following approaches previously used in the
190 scientific literature (Sandberg, 2003; U.S. Department of Transportation, 2015).

191 A microphone with a windshield was located 15 m from the centre of the road
192 (Sandberg, 2003) and at a height of 1.5 m from the ground, in order to make *in situ*
193 measurements, as shown in Fig. 1 (ISO 1996-2, 2017; Montes González et al., 2020c;
194 RSG, 2018). The equivalent sound pressure level was recorded in the broadband ($L_{eq,A}$)
195 and 1/3 octave bands (L_{Xeq}) using a class 1 sound level meter/analyser. Thirty-six 10-
196 minute measurements were carried out in two campaigns on different days. The
197 calibration of the sound level meter was verified before and after each series of
198 measurements.

199 The relative humidity, air temperature, wind speed and pavement temperature
200 were recorded at the beginning and end of each measurement. The relative humidity and
201 air temperature were measured at a height of 1.5 m above the ground (Anfosso-LédéE
202 and Pichaud, 2007; Bueno et al., 2011; Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011; ISO 11819-2,
203 2017) using a thermo-hygrometer sensor with an accuracy of $\pm 1\%$; this was placed in
204 the shade to ensure that direct sunlight did not affect the measurement. The pavement
205 temperature was measured using a thermal camera with a sensitivity of $<0.045^{\circ}\text{C}$
206 (reading temperature range -20 to $+120^{\circ}\text{C}$) at a single position on the side of the road
207 and across the nearest lane from the location of the sound level meter. The camera was
208 placed at a height of 1.5 m with an angle of 45° with respect to the horizontal. Before
209 and after each measurement, a thermal image of the traffic lane was taken on the tread.

210 The roadway temperatures were extracted from the thermal images, and the average was
211 calculated (Bueno et al., 2011).

212 **2.3. Data processing**

213 As explained previously, the deviations in sound level that are associated with
214 differences in speed and vehicle characteristics could be counterbalanced through the
215 use of an average sound pressure level recorded over a 10-minute period, during which
216 the number of vehicles registered was at least 100 (ISO 11819-1, 1997; ISO 1996-2,
217 2017). A similar average value of the sound power generated per vehicle unit is
218 expected for all of the measurements taken. However, the number of vehicles that pass
219 by is not expected to be the same in each 10-minute period. This means that the
220 equivalent continuous sound level recorded in each measurement period will be
221 influenced by the total number of vehicles that have passed in front of the microphone
222 during that period. To take this fact into account, it is necessary to normalise the results
223 against a reference flow. An average value of 780 vehicles/hour was recorded on site,
224 and the normalised sound pressure level L_N was obtained from Eq. (1):

$$225 \quad L_N = L_0 - 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{V_m}{780} \right) + 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{t_m}{60} \right) \quad (1)$$

226 where L_0 is the recorded sound pressure level; V_m is the total number of vehicles
227 recorded in 10 minutes; and t_m is the measurement time in minutes.

228 Although the proportion of non-light vehicles recorded is less than 10% overall,
229 the sound power emitted by these categories of vehicles can be considered different
230 from that of category 1 vehicles (Cho and Mun, 2008; Institute for Vehicle Technology,
231 2005). To examine the possible influence of these vehicles on the results, a second
232 normalisation was performed by considering the equivalence between the noise level
233 emitted by category 1 vehicles and the rest of the vehicle categories, as shown in Eq. 2.

234 The coefficients for vehicle categories 2, 3 and 4 in Eq. 2 were obtained by (Sandberg,
235 2003) based on a speed of 95 km/h for categories 1 and 4, and 90 km/h for categories 2
236 and 3.

$$237 V_{eq1} = V_{m1} + V_{m2} * 3.83 + V_{m3} * 6.31 + V_{m4} \quad (2)$$

238 where V_{eq1} is the equivalent total number of vehicles in category 1, and V_{mi} is the
239 number of vehicles in category i (European Directive, 2015).

240 Again, the total equivalent number of vehicles in category 1 is not likely to be the
241 same in each measurement, and another normalisation was therefore applied in order to
242 analyse the relationship between the measured noise level and the temperature. The
243 equivalent vehicle value V_{eq1} obtained from Eq. (2) was normalised based on the
244 average total equivalent category 1 vehicle flow in the measurements (a total equivalent
245 of 930 category 1 vehicles per hour). In a similar way as above, the category 1
246 equivalent normalised sound pressure level L_{Neq1} was derived from Eq. (3):

$$247 L_{Neq1} = L_0 - 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{V_{eq1}}{930} \right) + 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{t_m}{60} \right) \quad (3)$$

248 where L_0 is the recorded sound pressure level; V_{eq1} is the total number of equivalent
249 vehicles in category 1; and t_m is the measurement time in minutes.

250 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

251 3.1. Environmental and traffic variables

252 During the sound level measurements, the environmental variables of wind speed,
253 relative humidity and air and pavement temperatures (T_A) and (T_P) were recorded. The
254 wind speed was zero in most of the readings, and lower than 2 m/s even in the worst
255 case. The relative humidity varied between 27% and 63%. The air temperature ranged
256 from 22°C to 32°C, while the pavement temperature varied from 27°C to 53°C. A

257 significant linear relationship between the air and pavement temperatures was found (p
258 < 0.001), with a coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.93. This result is similar to values
259 reported by other authors (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007; Rochat, 2009).

260 The average traffic flow recorded on site was 130 vehicles per measurement (780
261 vehicles/h). The distribution by vehicle category was as follows: category 1: 93.46%;
262 category 2: 3.27%; category 3: 1.70%; and category 4: 1.57%.

263 3.2. Broadband analysis

264 As indicated in the methodology section, a study of the relationship between the
265 sound level and temperature required a normalisation of the sound levels in order to take
266 into account the differences in traffic flow during the measurement period. This
267 normalisation was carried out in two phases. Firstly, given the low traffic flows
268 measured for vehicle categories other than type 1, an average value for the sound power
269 per vehicle using Eq. 1 was assumed. Then, despite the low proportions of vehicle
270 categories 2, 3 and 4, the effect that their presence had on the relationship between noise
271 level and temperature was considered of interest. Eqs. 2 and 3 were used to carry out
272 this normalisation. The results for the relationships between the sound level and the
273 pavement and air temperatures are shown in Fig. 3 and Table 1.

274 Fig. 3(a) shows the linear relationship between the equivalent normalised sound
275 pressure level L_N and the pavement temperature T_p , which can explain 58% of the
276 variability of the measured sound level with a probability of more than 99.9% (see
277 Table 1). The coefficient of variation of the sound level with the temperature of the
278 pavement (β_p $dBA/^\circ C$) has a value of -0.051 ± 0.008 $dBA/^\circ C$, representing a decrease
279 in sound level with an increase in pavement temperature. The dependence of the sound
280 level on the air temperature was then analysed, and Fig. 3(b) shows a linear relationship

281 that explains 60% of the variability (p -value < 0.001). In this case, the coefficient of
282 variation obtained for the air temperature (β_A $dBA/_{\circ}C$) was -0.146 ± 0.020 $dBA/_{\circ}C$,
283 which, in terms of its absolute value, is clearly higher than that obtained for the
284 pavement temperature even considering its standard error. This increase in β is
285 evidently related to the smaller range of variation in the air temperature with respect to
286 the pavement temperature. Despite the close relationship between the two temperatures
287 ($R^2 = 0.93$), these findings reflect the importance of the physical media in which the
288 temperature is measured, in terms of determining the value of the coefficient of
289 dependence of the sound level on this environmental variable.

290 The effect of considering vehicles other than category 1 on the relationship
291 between sound level and temperature was then analysed using Eqs. 2 and 3. The results
292 for the relationship of the sound pressure level normalised to equivalent category 1
293 vehicles (L_{Neq1}) and the pavement temperature are shown in Fig. 3(c). The linear
294 relationship between these variables explains 66% of the variability in the measured
295 sound level as a function of pavement temperature, with a significance lower than
296 0.001; this represents an increase in the explanation of the variability of sound levels
297 when all categories of vehicles were considered. The β_p coefficient is equal to
298 -0.058 ± 0.007 $dBA/_{\circ}C$ in Fig. 3(c). A value of $\beta_A = -0.161 \pm 0.020$ $dBA/_{\circ}C$ was
299 found for the relationship between L_{Neq1} and T_A (Fig. 3(d)). This linear relationship can
300 explain 66% of the variability in the sound level with air temperature, with a p -value $<$
301 0.001. Hence, when air temperature is considered, this second normalisation (Eqs. 2 and
302 3) also provides an improvement in the explanation of the variability in the measured
303 sound levels. Although the values of the slopes of the lines shown in Fig. 3 (c) and Fig.

304 3 (d) are slightly higher than those in Fig. 3 (a) and Fig. 3 (b) in absolute values, this
 305 increase is not significant considering the standard error of the slopes.

306 Fig. 3. Scatter diagrams and linear regression between the normalised sound levels (L_N
 307 and L_{Neq1}) and temperature.

308 In summary, taking into consideration all of the vehicle categories improves the
 309 determination of noise emission levels as a function of either the pavement or the air
 310 temperature, even though the proportion of vehicles other than category 1 is low.

311

312 Table 1. Linear regression parameters between the sound pressure level and the air
 313 and pavement temperatures

Independent variable	Dependent variable	β_i (dBA/°C)	Standard error β_i (dBA/°C)	Constant (dBA)	R^2	Sig.
T_P	L_N	-0.051	0.008	65.5	0.58	< 0.001
T_P	L_{Neq1}	-0.058	0.007	65.8	0.66	< 0.001
T_A	L_N	-0.146	0.020	67.3	0.60	< 0.001
T_A	L_{Neq1}	-0.161	0.020	67.8	0.66	< 0.001

314

315 These results were then compared with those obtained in previous studies of
 316 pavements of the same type (Table 2) (Anfosso-Lédée and Pichaud, 2007; Bueno et al.,
 317 2011; Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011; Liao et al., 2015; Yuan et al., 2019). In this respect,
 318 it must be taken into consideration that this is a seven-year-old dense mixture. Some
 319 studies used the air temperature to obtain the coefficient of variation in the sound
 320 pressure level with temperature (Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011; Liao et al., 2015), while
 321 others derived the coefficient from the pavement temperature (Bueno et al., 2011; Yuan
 322 et al., 2019). Anfosso-Lédée and Pichaud (Anfosso-Lédée and Pichaud, 2007)
 323 determined the coefficients for both temperatures, in this case using the CPB method.
 324 They obtained a coefficient of variation in the sound level for a dense pavement of
 325 $-0.100 \text{ dBA}/^\circ\text{C}$ using the air temperature, and $-0.060 \text{ dBA}/^\circ\text{C}$ from the pavement
 326 temperature.

327 Of the researchers who examined only the air temperature, (Bühlmann and
 328 Ziegler, 2011) reported a coefficient of variation of -0.100 or $-0.110 \text{ dBA}/^\circ\text{C}$,
 329 depending on the type of tyre, using the CPX method, while Liao et al. (Liao et al.,
 330 2015) found a value of $-0.090 \text{ dBA}/^\circ\text{C}$ using the OBSI method.

331 Of the researchers who investigated only the pavement temperature, Bueno et al.
 332 (Bueno et al., 2011) obtained a coefficient of variation of $-0.060 \text{ dBA}/^\circ\text{C}$ from the

333 CPX method. Yuan et al. (Yuan et al., 2019) conducted a study using the CPB method
 334 in which they considered three driving speeds (40, 60 and 80 km/h) and two different
 335 vehicles, and calculated coefficients of variation of $-0.086 \text{ dBA}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-0.083 \text{ dBA}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
 336 and $-0.081 \text{ dBA}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for these three speeds, respectively.

337 For the air temperature, the results presented in this paper were above the range of
 338 variation reported in previous studies, which were conducted using standardised test
 339 methods and under controlled conditions in terms of the vehicles and tyre-road surface.
 340 The results obtained in this study for the dependence of sound level on pavement
 341 temperature were within the range of variation of previous investigations (Table 2).

342 When the coefficients of variation for the sound level with temperature (β_i)
 343 reported in the scientific literature are compared, higher values were obtained when the
 344 air temperature was considered rather than the pavement temperature; this broadly
 345 corresponds to the results of the present study, although the values of the coefficients
 346 found in this paper were greater than those in the literature.

347 Table 2. Regression and determination coefficients between the sound level and
 348 temperature reported in scientific literature

Publication	β_a	β_p	R^2	Method	Temperature range
	$\text{dBA}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$\text{dBA}/^{\circ}\text{C}$			
Present research L_N	-0.146	-0.051	0.58 / 0.60	Actual conditions of continuous vehicle flow	22-32 / 27-53
Present research L_{Neq1}	-0.161	-0.058	0.66 / 0.66		
(Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007)	-0.100	-0.060	0.92 / 0.86	CPB	0-30 / 0-50
(Bueno et al., 2011)	-	-0.060	- / n/d	CPX	- / 15-50
(Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011)	-0.100 / -0.110 ¹	-	0.8 / -	CPX	10-30 / -
(Liao et al., 2015)	-0.090	-	0.36 / -	OBSI	5-30 / -
(Yuan et al., 2019)	-	-0.086 / -0.081	- / n/d	SPB	- / 5-22

349

350 ¹ Depending on the type of tyre used

351 3.3. Spectral analysis

1
2
3 352 To provide a detailed analysis of the dependence of sound level on temperature,
4
5 353 the broadband analysis was complemented by a study in the 1/3 octave bands in the
6
7 354 range 50 Hz to 10 kHz. In the same way as for the broadband analysis, the sound
8
9
10 355 pressure levels were normalised to a reference flow L_N (Eq. 1) and to the equivalent
11
12 356 flow of category 1 vehicles L_{Neq1} (Eqs. 2 and 3). These calculations were carried out for
13
14
15 357 both the air and pavement temperatures.

16
17 358 Fig. 4 and Table 3 show the results for the relationship between L_N and the air and
18
19 359 pavement temperatures. In the case of Fig. 4 (b), considering that the number of data
20
21
22 360 used in the regression is the same for the different frequencies analysed, the value of the
23
24
25 361 coefficient of determination for which it was significant with a probability of 95%, 99%
26
27 362 and 99.9% was obtained. Thus, the horizontal lines in Fig. 4 (b) indicate the p -values of
28
29
30 363 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001. At low frequencies, significant relationships were observed in the
31
32 364 63 Hz and 160 Hz third octave bands for both temperatures (p -value < 0.05), although
33
34
35 365 with a low explanation of variability of between 15% and 17%. The slope at 63 Hz
36
37 366 implies a decrease in sound level with increasing temperature (-0.08 ± 0.03 dB/°C for
38
39 367 T_P and -0.22 ± 0.09 dB/°C for T_A), with similar behaviour to the broadband results. In
40
41
42 368 contrast, the slope found in the 160 Hz band is positive (0.06 ± 0.02 dB/°C for T_P and
43
44 369 0.16 ± 0.07 dB/°C for T_A), indicating an increase in sound level with increasing
45
46
47 370 temperature.

48
49 371 The next bands in which significant relationships were found corresponded to the
50
51 372 range 800 Hz to 3.15 kHz. The relationship between sound pressure level and
52
53
54 373 temperature in this band range is negative, and has a greater absolute value for air
55
56 374 temperature than for pavement temperature, for the same reasons as identified in the

375 broadband analysis. It was also observed that except for the 3.15 kHz band, the
 376 frequency bands showed correlations with a significance lower than 0.001, low standard
 377 errors of slopes, and high explanations of the variability in the sound level with
 378 temperature. The results in the third octave bands between 1 and 2 kHz are particularly
 379 remarkable, where the R^2 values varied between 0.65 and 0.83, indicating sound level
 380 variation coefficients ranging from -0.06 ± 0.01 to -0.09 ± 0.01 dB/°C for T_p and -0.16
 381 ± 0.02 to -0.26 ± 0.02 dB/°C for T_A (Table 3). For the rest of the high frequency bands,
 382 significant relationships (p -value < 0.05) were only found in the 10 kHz band for T_p .
 383 The explanation of the variability in the sound level was also low (11%) and a standard
 384 error of about 50% of the slope value.

385 Fig. 4. Regression and determination coefficients for the linear relationship between the
 386 normalised sound pressure level (L_N) and the air and pavement temperatures in the 1/3
 387 octave bands.

388

Table 3. Linear regression parameters (slope, standard error of slope, R^2 and p -

389

value of R^2) between the sound pressure level L_N in the 1/3 octave bands and the air and

390

pavement temperatures

Fr.	50Hz	63Hz	80Hz	100Hz	125Hz	160Hz	200Hz	250Hz	
Low frequencies			Pavement temperature						
m	0.07	-0.08	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.03	
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	
R²	0.08	0.16	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.17	0.09	0.04	
Sig.	n.s.	< 0.05	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05	n.s.	n.s.	
			Air temperature						
m	0.20	-0.22	0.05	0.09	0.10	0.16	0.10	0.06	
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.11	0.09	0.08	0.11	0.10	0.07	0.06	0.06	
R²	0.09	0.16	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.15	0.08	0.02	
Sig.	n.s.	< 0.05	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05	n.s.	n.s.	
Fr.	315Hz	400Hz	500Hz	630Hz	800Hz	1kHz	1.25kHz	1.6kHz	2kHz
Mid-frequencies			Pavement temperature						
m	0.04	0.05	0.00	-0.01	-0.04	-0.06	-0.07	-0.09	-0.09
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
R²	0.07	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.65	0.71	0.83	0.66
Sig.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Air temperature						
m	0.08	0.12	-0.04	-0.02	-0.10	-0.16	-0.19	-0.26	-0.24
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03
R²	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.38	0.67	0.72	0.82	0.65
Sig.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Fr.	2.5kHz	3.15kHz	4kHz	5kHz	6.3kHz	8kHz	10kHz		
High frequencies			Pavement temperature						
m	-0.07	-0.04	-0.03	0.00	0.01	0.01	-0.05		
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03		
R²	0.47	0.21	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.09		
Sig.	< 0.001	< 0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.		
			Air temperature						
m	-0.18	-0.12	-0.08	-0.02	0.02	0.00	-0.15		
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.07		
R²	0.47	0.23	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11		
Sig.	< 0.001	< 0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05		

391

392

Fig. 5 and Table 4 present the results for the relationships between the L_{Neq1}

393

values and the air and pavement temperatures. The horizontal lines in Fig. 5 (b) indicate

394

the different levels of significance of the coefficient of determination, analogous to Fig.

395

4 (b). In general, these show similarities to those obtained for L_N (Fig. 4 and Table 3).

396

At low frequencies, significant relationships with temperature were again found only for

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

397 sound levels measured in the 63 and 160 Hz bands. The slope was negative in the first
1
2 398 case ($\beta_P = -0.09 \pm 0.03 \text{ dB}/\text{°C}$; $\beta_A = -0.24 \pm 0.08 \text{ dB}/\text{°C}$), and positive in the
3
4
5 399 second ($\beta_P = 0.06 \pm 0.02 \text{ dB}/\text{°C}$; $\beta_A = 0.15 \pm 0.06 \text{ dB}/\text{°C}$). However, while the
6
7 400 significance in the 160 Hz band was still 95%, it improved to 99% in the 63 Hz band.
8
9 401 The next frequency range in which a significant relationship with temperature was
10
11 402 found appeared between 800 Hz and 3.15 kHz, with similar p -values to those found for
12
13 403 the previous normalisation. However, the results for the 800 Hz band were noteworthy,
14
15 404 as the variable L_{Neq1} could explain more than 50% of the variation in the sound level
16
17 405 with temperature, while the figure for the variable L_N was lower than 40%. For the rest
18
19 406 of the high-frequency bands, significant relationships (p -value < 0.05) were again only
20
21 407 found in the 10 kHz band, although in this case they applied to both temperatures.
22
23
24
25
26

27 408 When the results are analysed and both normalisations are compared, it can be
28
29 409 seen that the 1/3 octave bands of 63 and 800 Hz are the main ones at which the
30
31 410 combined effects of the different vehicle categories are the strongest; that is, it can be
32
33 411 said that the emission power in these bands behaves in a similar way to that indicated
34
35 412 for the equivalences considered for category 1 (Sandberg, 2003).
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

413 Fig. 5. Regression and determination coefficients for the linear relationship between the
 414 category 1 equivalent normalised sound pressure level (L_{Nequ1}) and the air and
 415 pavement temperatures in the 1/3 octave bands.

416 Table 4. Linear regression parameters (slope, standard error of slope, R^2 and p -
 417 value of R^2) between the category 1 equivalent normalised sound pressure level
 418 (L_{Nequ1}) in the 1/3 octave bands and the air and pavement temperatures

Fr.	50Hz	63Hz	80Hz	100Hz	125Hz	160Hz	200Hz	250Hz	
Low frequencies									
Pavement temperature									
m	0.06	-0.09	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.02	
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	
R^2	0.07	0.19	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.14	0.08	0.02	
Sig.	n.s.	< 0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05	n.s.	n.s.	
Air temperature									
m	0.19	-0.24	0.03	0.08	0.09	0.15	0.08	0.04	
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.10	0.06	0.05	0.06	
R^2	0.09	0.19	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.13	0.07	0.01	
Sig.	n.s.	< 0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05	n.s.	n.s.	
Fr.	315Hz	400Hz	500Hz	630Hz	800Hz	1kHz	1.25kHz	1.6kHz	2kHz
Mid-frequencies									
Pavement temperature									
m	0.04	0.04	-0.01	-0.01	-0.04	-0.06	-0.08	-0.10	-0.09
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
R^2	0.06	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.51	0.68	0.71	0.80	0.65
Sig.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Air temperature									
m	0.06	0.10	-0.06	-0.04	-0.12	-0.18	-0.21	-0.28	-0.26
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03
R^2	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.54	0.68	0.70	0.78	0.64
Sig.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Fr.	2.5kHz	3.15kHz	4kHz	5kHz	6.3kHz	8kHz	10kHz		
High frequencies									
Pavement temperature									
m	-0.07	-0.05	-0.03	-0.01	0.01	0.00	-0.06		
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03		
R^2	0.50	0.27	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.12		
Sig.	< 0.001	< 0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05		
Air temperature									
m	-0.20	-0.13	-0.10	-0.03	0.01	-0.01	-0.17		
$\hat{\sigma}_m$	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.07		
R^2	0.49	0.27	0.11	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.14		
Sig.	< 0.001	< 0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	< 0.05		

419 From a comparison between the findings of this research and those in the
 420 literature, it can be observed that several authors (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007;
 421 Bueno et al., 2011; Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011) have reported results with a similar
 422 trend for the range 800 to 3.15 kHz. The result for the 10 kHz band could not be
 423 compared with previous publications, as no analysis had been performed above 5 kHz

424 (Anfosso-LédéE and Pichaud, 2007; Bueno et al., 2011; Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011).
1
2 425 Regarding the results in the low-frequency bands, it is worth highlighting one paper
3
4 426 (Bühlmann and Ziegler, 2011) in which positive values were obtained for the
5
6 427 coefficients of variation in the sound pressure level with temperature, although this
7
8 428 result was discarded in the subsequent analysis. A. del Pizzo et al. (Del Pizzo et al.,
9
10 429 2020), in their study of the dependence of pavement texture on road traffic noise using
11
12 430 the CPX method, found a positive linear relationship between sound pressure level and
13
14 431 megatexture at low frequencies and negative at high frequencies associated with
15
16 432 macrotexture. This paper also indicated the relation between this behaviour and the
17
18 433 different generation mechanisms that dominate the two regions: tyre vibrations for low
19
20 434 frequency and aerodynamic mechanisms for high frequency. It seems therefore that the
21
22 435 low frequency emission range may require specific studies.
23
24
25
26
27
28

29 436 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

30
31

32
33 437 An experimental study of the relationship between the air and pavement
34
35 438 temperatures and the road traffic noise levels on a primary road under actual conditions
36
37 439 of continuous vehicle flow is presented in this manuscript. Several variables or
38
39 440 circumstances that can influence the measured sound level were taken into account.
40
41

42
43 441 Some key findings can be drawn from the broadband results. When the
44
45 442 temperature was taken at the road surface, the coefficients of variation in the sound
46
47 443 level with temperature were similar to those published in the scientific literature under
48
49 444 controlled conditions, following the reference standards. However, when the air
50
51 445 temperature was considered, the coefficients of variation in sound level with
52
53 446 temperature were higher than previously published results recorded under controlled
54
55 447 conditions in dense pavements. Despite the high proportion of light vehicles in the
56
57
58

448 mixed traffic on the road (over 92%), normalising to a flow of vehicles equivalent to
449 category 1 was found to improve the explanation of the variability of sound level with
450 temperature, regardless of the physical media in which the variable was measured.

451 Several conclusions could also be derived from the spectral analysis in the 1/3
452 octave bands. In the fundamental noise emission bands of road traffic, the trends in the
453 dependence of sound level on temperature coincided with the published outcomes,
454 resulting in a decrease of the sound level with increasing temperature. However, the
455 values of the coefficients of variation depended on the physical media in which the
456 temperature was measured. Thus, when the temperature of the pavement was measured,
457 the slopes were similar to those published in the scientific literature, while when the air
458 temperature was taken into account, the slopes were greater than those previously
459 reported. Another finding of note is the positive value of the coefficient of variation in
460 the sound level with temperature in the 160 Hz band, which implies an increase in the
461 sound level with increasing environmental temperature; this effect has not previously
462 been reported.

463 From a comparison of the spectral results with and without normalisation to
464 category 1 equivalent vehicles, no appreciable effects relating to the type of
465 normalisation were found in most frequency bands, in contrast to the results of the
466 broadband analysis. However, noticeable improvements were observed in the 1/3 octave
467 bands of 63 and 800 Hz and 3.15 kHz for the normalisation of vehicles equivalent to
468 category 1.

469 The results found in this study for traffic noise, obtained on a road in actual
470 conditions of use with dense asphalt and mixed and continuous flow of vehicles, are not
471 necessarily transferable to other types of pavements or flows. The possibility of
472 applying this type of study to the temperature corrections for strategic noise maps

473 indicates the need for further research with methodologies that allow to measure the
1 474 effect of temperature on the equivalent continuous sound level in other situations: other
2
3 475 types of asphalt, other types of flows, other proportions of light and heavy vehicles, etc.
4
5
6 476 In the other hand, the possible importance of the physical media in which the
7
8 477 environmental temperature is measured in terms of assessing the correction factors for
9
10 478 the effects of temperature on the sound level should be highlighted.
11
12

13 479 **Acknowledgements**

14
15
16
17 480 This work was co-financed by Consejería de Educación y Empleo of Junta de
18
19 481 Extremadura, the Extremadura Public Employment Service (SEXPE) and European
20
21 482 Union (FSE) through grants to promote the hiring of research support personnel in the
22
23 483 Autonomous Community of Extremadura (PAI20/40).
24
25

26
27 484 This project was co-financed by European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)
28
29 485 and Junta de Extremadura (GR18107, IB18050 and GR18053).
30
31

32 486 This work was also supported by Consejería de Economía, Ciencia y Agenda
33
34 487 Digital of Junta de Extremadura and European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)
35
36 488 through grants for the financing of industrial research and experimental development
37
38 489 projects (IDA-19-0022-3).
39
40

41 490 This work was also supported by Consejería de Economía, Ciencia y Agenda
42
43 491 Digital of Junta de Extremadura, European Union and European Social Fund (ESF)
44
45 492 through grants for the strengthening of R&D&I through the mobility of postdoctoral
46
47 493 researchers (PO17014) and by Consejería de Economía, Ciencia y Agenda Digital of
48
49 494 Junta de Extremadura through grants for attracting and returning research talent to
50
51 495 R&D&I centres belonging to the Extremadura Science, Technology and Innovation
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

496 System (TA18019), where University of Extremadura was the beneficiary entity in both
497 cases.

498 **REFERENCES**

- 499 Andersson, E.M., Ögren, M., Molnár, P., Segersson, D., Rosengren, A., Stockfelt, L.,
500 2020. Road traffic noise, air pollution and cardiovascular events in a Swedish
501 cohort. *Environ. Res.* 185, 109446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109446>
- 502 Anfosso-LédéE, F., Pichaud, Y., 2007. Temperature effect on tyre-road noise. *Appl.*
503 *Acoust.* 68, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2006.06.001>
- 504 Barrigón Morillas, J.M., Montes González, D., Gómez Escobar, V., Rey Gozalo, G.,
505 Vílchez-Gómez, R., 2021. A proposal for producing calculated noise mapping
506 defining the sound power levels of roads by street stratification. *Environ. Pollut.*
507 270, 116080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116080>
- 508 Bueno, M., Luong, J., Viñuela, U., Terán, F., Paje, S.E., 2011. Pavement temperature
509 influence on close proximity tire/road noise. *Appl. Acoust.* 72, 829–835.
510 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2011.05.005>
- 511 Bühlmann, E., Sandberg, U., Mioduszewski, P., 2015. Speed dependency of
512 temperature effects on road traffic noise, in: *Proc. of Inter-Noise*.
- 513 Bühlmann, E., Van Blokland, G., 2014. Temperature effects on tyre/road-noise-A
514 review of empirical research, in: *Proceedings of Forum Acusticum*. Carcovia,
515 Poland, pp. 1–6.
- 516 Bühlmann, E., Ziegler, T., 2011. Temperature effects on tyre/road noise measurements,
517 in: *40th International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering*
518 2011, INTER-NOISE 2011. Osaka Japan, september 4-7, pp. 557–564.
- 519 Cai, Y., Zijlema, W.L., Sjørgjerd, E.P., Doiron, D., de Hoogh, K., Hodgson, S.,

- 520 Wolffenbuttel, B., Gulliver, J., Hansell, A.L., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., Rahimi, K.,
1 521 Kvaløy, K., 2020. Impact of road traffic noise on obesity measures: Observational
2 study of three European cohorts. *Environ. Res.* 191, 110013.
3 522
4 523 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110013>
5 6 524 Cho, D.S., Mun, S., 2008. Study to analyze the effects of vehicles and pavement surface
7 types on noise. *Appl. Acoust.* 69, 833–843.
8 9 525
10 526 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2007.04.006>
11 12 527 Connelly, F., Johnsson, R.D., Aulsebrook, A.E., Mulder, R.A., Hall, M.L., Vyssotski,
13 14 A.L., Lesku, J.A., 2020. Urban noise restricts, fragments, and lightens sleep in
15 16 528 Australian magpies. *Environ. Pollut.* 267, 115484.
17 18 529
19 20 530 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115484>
21 22 531 Del Pizzo, A., Teti, L., Moro, A., Bianco, F., Fredianelli, L., Licitra, G., 2020. Influence
23 24 of texture on tyre road noise spectra in rubberized pavements. *Appl. Acoust.* 159,
25 26 532 107080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2019.107080>
27 28 533
29 30 534 European Directive, 2015. Commission Directive (EU) 2015/996 of 19 May 2015
31 32 establishing common noise assessment methods according to Directive
33 34 535 2002/49/EC. European Union.
35 36 536
37 38 537 European Directive, 2002. Directive 2002/49/EC of the European Parliament and of the
39 40 Council of 25 June 2002 Relating to the Assessment and Management of
41 42 538 Environmental Noise (END).
43 44 539
45 46 540 Finch, D., Schofield, H., Mathews, F., 2020. Traffic noise playback reduces the activity
47 48 and feeding behaviour of free-living bats. *Environ. Pollut.* 263, 114405.
49 50 541
51 52 542 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114405>
53 54 543 Franklin, M., Fruin, S., 2017. The role of traffic noise on the association between air
55 56 pollution and children's lung function. *Environ. Res.* 157, 153–159.
57 58 544

545 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.05.024>

1
2 546 Fredianelli, L., Del Pizzo, A., Licitra, G., 2019. Recent developments in sonic crystals

3
4 547 as barriers for road traffic noise mitigation. *Environ. - MDPI* 6, 14.

5
6 548 <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6020014>

7
8 549 Iglesias-Merchán, C., Diaz-Balteiro, L., de la Puente, J., 2016. Road traffic noise impact

9
10 550 assessment in a breeding colony of cinereous vultures (*Aegypius monachus*) in

11
12 551 Spain. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 139, 1124–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4943553>

13
14 552 Institute for Vehicle Technology, 2005. Investigations on Noise Emission of Motor

15
16 553 Vehicles in Road Traffic. Wuerselen, Germany,.

17
18 554 ISO/PAS 11819-4, 2013. Acoustics — Method for measuring the influence of road

19
20 555 surfaces on traffic noise — Part 4: SPB method using backing board.

21
22 556 ISO/TS 13471-1, 2017. Acoustics — Temperature influence on tyre/road noise

23
24 557 measurement — Part 1: Correction for temperature when testing with the CPX

25
26 558 method.

27
28 559 ISO 11819-1, 1997. Acoustics — Measurement of the influence of road surfaces on

29
30 560 traffic noise — Part 1: Statistical Pass-By method.

31
32 561 ISO 11819-2, 2017. Acoustics — Measurement of the influence of road surfaces on

33
34 562 traffic noise — Part 2: The close-proximity method.

35
36 563 ISO 1996-1, 2016. Acoustics — Description, measurement and assessment of

37
38 564 environmental noise — Part 1: Basic quantities and assessment procedures.

39
40 565 ISO 1996-2, 2017. Acoustics — Description, measurement and assessment of

41
42 566 environmental noise — Part 2: Determination of sound pressure levels.

43
44 567 ISO 9613-1, 1993. Acoustics — Attenuation of sound during propagation outdoors —

45
46 568 Part 1: Calculation of the absorption of sound by the atmosphere.

47
48 569 ISO 9613-2, 1996. Acoustics — Attenuation of sound during propagation outdoors —

- 570 Part 2: General method of calculation. International Organization for
571 Standardization,.
- 572 Jabben, J., 2013. Temperature effects on road traffic noise measurements. *J. Basic Appl.*
573 *Phys.* 2, 43–46.
- 574 Khan, J., Ketzler, M., Jensen, S.S., Gulliver, J., Thysell, E., Hertel, O., 2021.
575 Comparison of Road Traffic Noise prediction models: CNOSSOS-EU, Nord2000
576 and TRANEX. *Environ. Pollut.* 270, 116240.
577 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116240>
- 578 Kneib, G., Belcher, D., Beckenbauer, T., Beyeler, H.P., 2016. Continuous road traffic
579 noise monitoring and aging of asphalt surfaces, in: *Proceedings of the INTER-*
580 *NOISE 2016 - 45th International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control*
581 *Engineering: Towards a Quieter Future*. pp. 7122–7133.
- 582 Lan, Y., Roberts, H., Kwan, M.P., Helbich, M., 2020. Transportation noise exposure
583 and anxiety: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Environ. Res.* 191, 110118.
584 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110118>
- 585 Lan, Z., Cai, M., 2021. Dynamic traffic noise maps based on noise monitoring and
586 traffic speed data. *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 94, 102796.
587 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2021.102796>
- 588 Liao, G., Heitzman, M., West, R., Wang, S., Ai, C., 2015. Temperature Effects on the
589 Correlations between Tire-Pavement Noises and Pavement Surface Characteristics,
590 in: *New Frontiers in Road and Airport Engineering - Selected Papers from the*
591 *2015 International Symposium on Frontiers of Road and Airport Engineering,*
592 *IFRAE 2015*. pp. 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784414255.021>
- 593 Licitra, G., Teti, L., Cerchiai, M., Bianco, F., 2017. The influence of tyres on the use of
594 the CPX method for evaluating the effectiveness of a noise mitigation action based

- 595 on low-noise road surfaces. *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 55, 217–226.
- 596 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.07.002>
- 597 Ma, H., Wen, M., Xu, L., Zhang, Z., 2021. Contingent valuation of road traffic noise: A
598 case study in China. *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 93, 102765.
599 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2021.102765>
- 600 Memoli, G., Paviotti, M., Kephelopoulos, S., Licitra, G., 2008. Testing the acoustical
601 corrections for reflections on a façade. *Appl. Acoust.* 69, 479–495.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2007.05.006>
- 603 Ministry of Transport of Spain, 2015. Parte 5ª Firmes. Pliego de Prescripciones
604 Técnicas Generales para Obras de Carreteras y Puentes (PG-3).
- 605 Montes-González, D., Barrigón-Morillas, J.M., Escobar, V.G., Vílchez-Gómez, R.,
606 Rey-Gozaló, G., Atanasio-Moraga, P., Méndez-Sierra, J.A., 2019. Environmental
607 noise around hospital areas: A case study. *Environ. - MDPI* 6, 41.
608 <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6040041>
- 609 Montes González, D., Barrigón Morillas, J.M., Rey Gozaló, G., Atanasio Moraga, P.,
610 2020a. Microphone position and noise exposure assessment of building façades.
611 *Appl. Acoust.* 160, 107157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2019.107157>
- 612 Montes González, D., Barrigón Morillas, J.M., Rey Gozaló, G., Godinho, L., 2020b.
613 Effect of parking lanes on assessing the impact of road traffic noise on building
614 façades. *Environ. Res.* 184, 109299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109299>
- 615 Montes González, D., Barrigón Morillas, J.M., Rey Gozaló, G., Godinho, L., 2020c.
616 Evaluation of exposure to road traffic noise: Effects of microphone height and
617 urban configuration. *Environ. Res.* 191, 110055.
618 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110055>
- 619 Paschalidou, A.K., Kassomenos, P., Chonianaki, F., 2019. Strategic Noise Maps and

620 Action Plans for the reduction of population exposure in a Mediterranean port city.
621 Sci. Total Environ. 654, 144–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.048>
622 Puyana-Romero, V., Cueto, J.L., Gey, R., 2020. A 3D GIS tool for the detection of
623 noise hot-spots from major roads. *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 84,
624 102376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102376>
625 Rey Gozalo, G., Gómez Escobar, V., Barrigón Morillas, J.M., Montes González, D.,
626 Atanasio Moraga, P., 2019. Statistical attribution of errors in urban noise
627 modeling. *Appl. Acoust.* 15, 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2019.04.001>
628 Rochat, J.L., 2009. Investigation of temperature correction for wayside tire/pavement
629 noise measurements, 38th International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control
630 Engineering 2009, INTER-NOISE 2009.
631 RSG, 2018. Noise Measurement Handbook - Final Report. FHWA-HEP-18-065. U.S.
632 Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration, New Jersey.
633 Sandberg, U., 2015. Standardized corrections for temperature influence on tire/road
634 noise, in: Maling G., B.C. (Ed.), 44th International Congress and Exposition on
635 Noise Control Engineering, INTER-NOISE 2015, 9 August 2015 through 12
636 August 2015. Environment, Society, environment and transport, Swedish National
637 Road and Transport Research Institute.
638 Sandberg, U., 2003. Vehicle categories for description of noise source, in:
639 HARMONOISE (20003).
640 Thacher, J.D., Hvidtfeldt, U.A., Poulsen, A.H., Raaschou-Nielsen, O., Ketznel, M.,
641 Brandt, J., Jensen, S.S., Overvad, K., Tjønneland, A., Münzel, T., 2020. Long-term
642 residential road traffic noise and mortality in a Danish cohort. *Environ. Res.* 187,
643 109633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109633>
644 U.S. Department of Transportation, 2015. Traffic Noise Model (TNM).

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

645 Van Blokland, G., Tollenaar, C., Van Loon, R., 2014. Report on Acoustic Aging of
646 Road Surfaces, in: Conference of European Directors of Roads. pp. 1–66.

647 Vázquez, V. F., Terán, F., Huertas, P., Paje, S.E., 2018. Field assessment of a Cold-In
648 place-recycled pavement: Influence on rolling noise. *J. Clean. Prod.* 197, 154–162.
649 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.192>

650 Vázquez, Víctor F., Terán, F., Huertas, P., Paje, S.E., 2018. Surface aging effect on
651 tire/pavement noise medium-term evolution in a medium-size city. *Coatings* 8,
652 206. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings8060206>

653 Wosniacki, G.G., Zannin, P.H.T., 2021. Framework to manage railway noise exposure
654 in Brazil based on field measurements and strategic noise mapping at the local
655 level. *Sci. Total Environ.* 757, 143721.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143721>

657 Yuan, M., Ni, D., Zhang, D., Wei, X., Wang, Z., Wang, C., 2019. Effect of temperature
658 on road pass-by noise of light vehicle, in: *IOP Conference Series: Earth and
659 Environmental Science*. IOP Publishing, p. 22003.